
Emotional Intelligence and Performance of Academic Staff in Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria.

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the effect of Emotional Intelligence and Performance of Academic Staff in Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria. Relevant conceptual, theoretical and empirical literature was reviewed taking cognizance of the problem and the hypotheses of the study. The study was anchored on multiple intelligences theory and social cognitive theory. Descriptive research survey design was adopted in this study and primary source of data was obtained from the respondents, using instrument designed on a five-point Likert scale. The population of the study comprised 13, 163 academic staff in federal universities in south east, Nigeria. The sample size consisted of 341 academic staff in federal universities in south east, Nigeria. Krejcie and Morgan was used to obtain the sample size. Face and content validity method was used to ensure validity of the instrument. The reliability of the instrument was achieved through test re-rest method. Simple percentage analysis was employed to answer the research questions. Linear regression analysis was conducted to assess the relative predictive power of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The hypotheses tested showed that self-awareness has significant positive effect on employee task performance ($\beta=.049$, $P=0.003 < 0.05$). Self-regulation has significant positive effect on employee adaptive performance ($\beta=0.047$, $P=0.000 < 0.05$). Self-motivation has significant positive effect on employee contextual performance ($\beta=0.147$, $P=0.001 < 0.05$). Empathy has no significant positive effect on employee counterproductive work behavior ($\beta=0.101$, $P=0.058 > 0.05$). Relationship management has significant positive effect on employee proactive work behavior ($\beta=0.164$, $P=0.001 < 0.05$). And social skills has significant positive effect on employee creativity ($\beta=0.102$, $P=0.000 < 0.05$). 'The study concluded that understanding emotions and developing emotion regulation can help achieve educational goals and objectives and improve academic staff performance in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria'. The study recommended that Nigerian university management should create more awareness about the importance of self-awareness among their staff through effective training of academic staff on self-awareness competencies. Federal universities in the South East, should prioritize management leadership training with a focus on developing the adaptive behavior of employees. Academic staff at the universities should prioritize building strong relationship with their colleagues, students, and management, which will enhance their work strength and contribute to a friendly environment.

Keyword: Emotional Intelligence; performance of Academic Staff, Federal Universities; South East, Nigeria

1.1 Introduction

Academic success or performance by teachers in educational organizations like university is a key goal in the development of all educational programs. University education is designed to create and impart knowledge, with the aim of solving societal problems and fostering development. The vision of many Federal Universities in Nigeria is to harness teaching, research, and public service to address societal challenges. University education is thus a vital stage of education essential for achieving national development, as it is improbable for any nation to progress without it. Attaining the objectives of university education is heavily reliant on the performance of its academic staff, who play a vital and tireless role in generating and disseminating knowledge. Federal university education is crucial for the success of individuals across various disciplines, as it equips them with diverse knowledge and skills that foster excellence, physical preparedness, and mental development. These skills include creativity, critical thinking, and motivation. To effectively impact these skills, academic staff in federal universities must possess a deep understanding of their students' emotional landscapes, including their feelings, challenges, and needs, which are fundamental aspects of emotional intelligence.

Giardini and Frese (2016) defines emotion as a felt tendency or a state of feeling that an individual experiences. Emotions can manifest in both negative and positive ways. Negative emotions, in particular, can significantly impact our daily lives and cloud our judgment, leading to unfair decisions that may also influence those around us. On the other hand, positive emotions could help to regulate one's emotions accurately, change one's behavior in the desired manner thereby enhance academic performance. It is from emotions that the concept of emotional intelligence (EI) is built. Emotional Intelligence refers to the ability of a person to perceive emotions, access knowledge, reflectively regulate emotions, and promote emotional and intellectual growth (Salovey, 2019). Mayer (2018) defines it as one's ability to understand and regulate one's emotional responses as well as to adapt and respond to others. This basic understanding affects the way people relate peacefully and effectively in their jobs and other spheres of life. The ability of people to live and relate harmoniously with one another, despite their emotional differences, is essentially what emotional intelligence is all about. In a nutshell, emotional intelligence refers to this ability, which has been identified as a crucial factor for organizational performance and success. Davis (2019) asserts that EI in the workplace can have positive impact on employee's performance, retention and occupational stress in which the company that cultivates EI in the workplace experiences greater profitability. Following this line of thought, freshman and Rubino (2020) perceive EI as one important aspect in educating an individual that passes through federal university education in Nigeria. According to them, emotional intelligence is defined as the ability to perceive, appraise, and express emotions accurately; access and/or generate feelings when they facilitate thought; comprehend emotional knowledge; and facilitate intellectual growth. There are six dimensions of emotional intelligence classified to self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy, relationship management and social skills.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Federal universities in Nigeria seem to be grappling with the challenges of emotional intelligence, emotional intelligence such as self-awareness, self-regulation self-motivation, empathy, relationship management, and social skills are important and cannot be done away with in the teaching profession, but seem not to be taken cognizance of sometimes neglected and abandoned in the federal universities. Jamroz (2019) observed that various problems of maladjustment in the workplace are due to poorly developed emotional intelligence, which, when developed, helps academic staff respond to a variety of environmental situations. The

inability of academic staff to exhibit emotional traits such as self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy, relationship management, and social skills could lead to psychological and physical implications that negatively impact their overall well-being. This could further impact on the system effectiveness and productivity and reduce the academic staff performance and expertise they were trained to offer. Based on this premise, the study examined the effect of emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff in federal universities in South East, Nigeria.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The broad objective of this study is to examine the effect of emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff in federal universities in South East, Nigeria. The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Examine the effect of self-awareness on employee task performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.
2. Investigate the effect of self-regulation on employee adaptive performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.
3. Determine the influence of self-motivation on employee contextual performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.
4. Examine the effect of empathy on employee counterproductive work behaviour in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.
5. Investigate the effect of relationship management on proactive work behaviour in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.
6. Assess the effect of social skills on employee creativity in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

1.4 Research Questions

To achieve the specific objectives stated above, this work will answer the following research questions:

1. To what extent does self-awareness affect employee task performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria?
2. What is the effect of self-regulation on employee adaptive performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria?
3. To what degree does self-motivation influence employee contextual performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria?
4. To what extent does empathy affect employee counterproductive work behavior in federal universities in south east, Nigeria?
5. How does relationship management affect employee proactive work behavior in federal universities in south east, Nigeria?
6. What is the effect of social skills on employee creativity in federal universities in south east, Nigeria?

1.5 Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to give direction to this study:

H₀₁: Self-awareness has no significant positive effect on employee task performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

H₀₂: Self-regulation has no significant positive effect on employee adaptive performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

H₀₃: Self-motivation has no significant positive influence on employee contextual performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

H₀₄: Empathy has no significant positive effect on employee counterproductive work behavior in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

H₀₅: Relationship management has no significant positive effect on employee proactive work behavior in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

H₀₆: Social skills have no significant positive effect on employee creativity in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study is significant in the sense that it will be useful to all universities in Nigeria and beyond. In specifics,

Students and Scholars: The findings of this study will be of immense benefit to students and scholars, as emotional intelligence in their university experience will have a profound impact on their personal and professional development, ultimately contributing to their success in life.

Management: The study will enlighten university management about the importance and key areas where emotional intelligence is essential for effective management in Nigerian universities.

Academic staff: To the staff, especially the academic staff, the study will enhance the understanding of emotional intelligence among staff and how its practice influences their performance.

Policy Makers: The outcome of this study will be relevant to policy makers in Federal Universities in Nigeria, as it provides insights into management shortcomings and the extent to which emotional intelligence is compromised at the expense of academic performance. The study will motivate policy review and pave the way to enhance academic performance in Nigerian education.

Researchers and Academics: This research is also significant because it is expected to contribute to the existing literature on emotional Intelligence and its effect on various aspects of human behavior and performance.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The content scope of the study covered emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff in Federal Universities in South East, Nigeria. In addition, the unit scope of the study includes academic staff of the five federal Universities in South East, Nigeria, because they are the line officers whose activities impact directly on the students.

1.8 Limitation of this study

This study was limited to exploring the effect of emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff in federal universities in South East, Nigeria. As with any research endeavor, this was not immune to constraints. Some of the limitations included:

- Initial uncooperative attitude from some respondent, which was addressed by clarifying the academic purpose of the study and ensuring confidentiality.
- Incomprehensive completion of questionnaires by some respondents, resulting in incomplete or unreturned questionnaires.
- Challenges in collecting distributed questionnaires, which were mitigated with the assistance of a research assistant.

Despite these limitations, the study aimed to provide valuable insights into the effect of emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff in federal universities in South East, Nigeria

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.0 Conceptual Review

2.1 Emotional Intelligence

American psychologist and science journalist Daniel Goleman is one of the most inventive writers on the topic of emotional intelligence. From the standpoint of writers, emotional intelligence (EI) has several meanings. Giao, Vuong, Huan, Tushar, and Quan, (2020) defined emotional intelligence is an important factor in an individual's performance and success in work and family roles.

In the same vein, Adriano and Callaghan (2020) view emotional intelligence as a managerial tool for problem-solving, coping with pressure from work and family, coping with changes in customers' demands constant changes in technology, and the ability to develop relationships. Emotional intelligence is the ability to distinguish between different feelings and identify and understand them to communicate effectively, empathize with others, relieve stress, conquer challenges, and defuse conflict.

Conceptual Model

Source: Model; Daniel Goleman's model of emotional intelligence (1995) and Model of Employee performance by Koopmans, Berhnaards, Hildebrandt, vet, & Berk (2014).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study was anchored on multiple intelligences theory and Social cognitive theory.

2.2.1 The Multiple Intelligences Theory

The multiple intelligences theory was developed by Howard Gardner 1983. This theory posits that individuals possess various abilities and aptitudes, which Gardner identified as nine distinct types: musical–rhythmic, visual-spatial, verbal-linguistic, logical-mathematical, Bodily-kinesthetic, interpersonal, and intrapersonal, naturalistic, and existential. These intelligences or competencies relate to a person’s unique aptitude and capabilities, as well as their preferred methods of demonstrating intellectual abilities. This theory identified that an interpersonally intelligent person has the ability to detect and respond appropriately to the moods, motivations and desires of others. Equally an intrapersonal intelligent person has the capacity to be self-aware and in tune with the inner feelings, values, beliefs and thinking processes.

The implication of this theory for the study are that when academic staff possess and demonstrate interpersonal and intrapersonal intelligences, it enhance their self-regulation, self-awareness and empathy levels, which in turn fosters positive relationships with their students, promotes student academic growth and development, and ultimately impacts organizational performance.

2.2.2 Social Cognitive Theory

Social cognitive theory was propounded by Albert Bandura 1986, the theory posits that learning occurs in a social context characterized by a dynamic and reciprocal interaction between the person, environment, and behavior. A unique feature of social cognitive theory is its emphasis on social influence and external and internal social reinforcement. This theory considers the unique way in which individuals acquire and maintain behavior, while also considering the social environment in which individuals perform the behavior. The theory takes into account a person’s past experiences, which factor into whether behavioral action will occur. These past experiences influences reinforcements, expectations, and expectancies, all of which shape whether a person will engage in a specific behavior and the reasons why a person engages in that behavior. It equally holds that portions of an individual’s knowledge acquisition can be directly related to observing others within the context of social interaction, experience and outside media influences.

This theory is significant to the study because the university is a learning environment where people learn by observing others. Since psychological and developmental research indicates that nurture plays a role in developing emotional intelligence (EI), it can be improved through training programs that target the relevant areas of the brain. Consequently, this learned behavior will be central to the personality development of both students and employees.

2.3 Theoretical Exposition

2.3.1 Self-Awareness and Employee Task Performance

There is a significant relationship between self-awareness and employee task performance. Research has consistently shown that employees with high self-awareness tend to perform better on tasks and have improved job performance overall. Here are some specific relationships;

- 1) **Improved goal-setting:** Self-awareness helps employees set realistic goals, leading to increased task performance and job satisfaction.
- 2) **Enhanced self-regulation:** Self-awareness enables employees to manage their emotions, motivation, and behaviors, leading to more effective task performance.

- 3) **Better time management:** Self-awareness helps employees prioritize tasks, allocate time and resources more efficiently, and avoid procrastination.
- 4) **Increased adaptability:** Self-awareness allows employees to adjust their approach to tasks based on their strengths, weaknesses, and learning style.
- 5) **Enhanced creativity:** Self-awareness fosters a deeper understanding of one's own thought processes, leading to more innovative and creative solutions.
- 6) **Improved communication:** Self-awareness helps employees communicate their needs, expectations, and limitations more effectively, leading to better teamwork and collaboration.

2.4 Empirical Review

Kang'ethe and Waiganjo (2023) examined relationship between self-awareness and organizational performance in public universities in Kenya and Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology. The objective was to study the relationship of self-awareness and organizational performance in public universities in Kenya: A Case Study of Jomo Kenyatta University of Agriculture and Technology. This study used both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Primary data was collected using structured questionnaires. The target population was the employees of JKUAT. Stratified random sampling was applied. Data was collected and analysed using descriptive statistics and was presented in form of tables and figures. The research project used descriptive research design and correlation analysis. The presentation of the study was in alignment with the research objectives, the dependent and independent variables. The findings were presented in forms of tables and figures indicated that self-awareness has a significant relationship with performance. The study revealed that employees were aware of their feelings and how they affect their performance. The study therefore recommends that employees need to feel as part of the institution. They need to feel like their views or opinions are considered, that their output impacts the institution, that their presence is valued in the institution. This can be done by coming up with team building activities, social interactions within the institution. Interaction can be enhanced by recognizing individual efforts by employees, giving accolades where necessary, promotion of employees as per the University policies and giving certificates of recognition. Secondly, institution should consider recognizing the value of self-awareness and ensuring that the employees understand its importance among the employees. This will help the employees know how to handle relationships between themselves, between themselves and the management and between themselves and the students (who are our core customers).

Mwangi, Kitainge and Nyabuto (2023) conducted the Relationship between Self-Motivation and Student Academic Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Nyeri County. The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between Self Esteem and student academic performance. The study was anchored on The Marsh/Shavelson model selfconcept. The study employed Ex-post facto research design. The study targeted students from public secondary schools in Nyeri County. Krejcie and Morgan (1970) formula was used to calculate the sample size of the students while Purposive sampling was used to select 25 teacher counselors making a total of 409 respondents. Data was collected using questionnaires, interview schedules and document analysis. The quantitative data from the questionnaire was first be subjected to preliminary processing through validation, coding and tabulation in readiness for analysis with the help of the statistical package for social science (SPSS) to analyze data. Descriptive statistics was presented using frequencies and percentages. Pearson Correlation Coefficient was employed to determine relationship that exists between the independent (Self-motivation) variables and dependent variable (student

academic performance). In addition, regression analysis was employed to test the relationships in the study. Qualitative data was transcribed, thematically classified and arranged before they are reported in narrations and quotations according to research objectives. Major findings from the study indicated that there was a significant positive correlation between Self-esteem and student academic performance ($r = .800$; $p = .000$) showing a strong correlation between Self-esteem and student academic performance. This study therefore, recommended that there is need for the teachers and education stakeholders in the ministry of education and beyond should give great attention to student self-concept as it affects student academic performance in schools and that schools should promote self-advocacy skills. Strong advocacy skills lead to greater self-confidence. It is also important for the teachers to understand student background. Schools should design effective feedback mechanism to encourage students to compare present performance against a goal and also against previous performance.

Gunasekara, Turner, Fung, and Stough, (2022) examined the Impact of lecturers' emotional intelligence on students' learning and engagement in remote learning spaces: A cross-cultural study. The study investigated students' perception of lecturers' EI during online learning using an Australian and Malaysian higher education. A qualitative thematic approach was used to answer the research questions. However, based on our findings, it is clear that certain aspects of the impact, such as opening cameras and how students like to approach lecturers to ask questions, are culturally dependent. The results revealed that there is a need for higher education institutions to support lecturers in EI skills and strategies training, including the application of EI skills and strategies in online teaching and learning contexts. Moreover, the results also revealed Such EI training for lecturers needs to include perceiving, understanding and managing both students' and their own emotions. The study recommends that the lecturers' EI could help them to better manage their learning and engage in the remote learning space.

Lang, and Saurage-Altenloh (2023) examined emotional intelligence as a predictor of employee engagement: A Study of U.S. Manufacturing workers. The study examined the extent to which EI and its dimensions predict EE and its facets in U.S. manufacturing workers. The research study used a quantitative methodology incorporating non experimental reasoning in a predictive, cross-sectional survey using linear and hierarchical multiple regression analyses to analyze the data. Findings from the study demonstrate a strong positive relationship between EI and its dimensions and EE and EI and its dimensions and vigor. However, EI and its dimensions of SEA and UOE exhibited a significant relationship with dedication, but OEA and ROE did not; EI showed a significant relationship with absorption, but SEA, OEA, UOE, and ROE did not. Therefore, the study recommends that leaders in manufacturing organizations may find influential when considering hiring practices, EI initiatives, and engagement efforts in the workplace.

Ademola, Inegbedion, Adebajji and Ighomereho (2022) conducted compulsory citizenship behavior, Work-life balance, and Turnover intention in academia: Mediating effects of emotional intelligence. This research investigates the mediating effects of emotional intelligence on the relationship between compulsory citizenship behavior, work-life balance, and turnover intention in the Nigerian academic environment. Questionnaires were used to collect data from the faculties of selected universities in Nigeria. Survey questionnaires were used to collect data from 600 faculties; but only 420 responded, a response rate of 70%. The results of structural equation modeling (SEM) show that compulsory citizenship behavior ($\beta = .15$; $t = 3.63$; $p < .05$) is positively and significantly associated with turnover intention

while work-life balance ($\beta = -.02$; $t = -.73$; $p > .05$) has a negative and insignificant relationship with turnover intention. The results further indicate that emotional intelligence ($\beta = .51$; $t = 10.91$; $p < .05$) is directly related to turnover intention. It was also found that emotional intelligence partially mediates between compulsory citizenship behavior and turnover intention ($\beta = .20$; $p < .05$), but not between work-life balance and turnover intention ($\beta = -.00$; $p > .05$). In addition, emotional intelligence moderates the relationship between compulsory citizenship behavior, work-life balance, and turnover intention. The findings suggest that emotional intelligence is bidirectional related to compulsory citizenship behavior, work-life balance, and turnover intention. The results provide valuable insights that can be used by university management to enhance wellbeing among the staff and reduce turnover intentions by minimizing the negative effects of compulsory citizenship behavior.

Olusoyi, Mahmoud, Afzal, and Nurhanisah (2023) examined the role of social media engagement and emotional intelligence in successful employment. This study focuses on demonstrating the role of social media engagement and considering emotional intelligence (hereafter EI) as a critical concept to successful employment. The study adopted a qualitative approach through semi-structured in-depth interviews of some randomly selected university students in the UK, young adults aged 19–32. The participants were selected based on different demographics to provide a broader and less biased representation of young adults in the UK. The results revealed that individuals mainly consider online communication instead of face-to-face communication. As a result, this situation could lead to low emotional intelligence skills since individuals do not interact. Thus, organizations need to consider creating virtual teams and work for successful employment. Another finding is that cultural differences and communicating with individuals from different backgrounds provide an inclusionary environment. In addition, the researchers' findings demonstrate that individuals consider social media as a tool that could bring reputation. The study recommends that recruitment organizations should introduce the latest requirements and trends of employers to ensure that the expectations of employers and potential candidates are aligned to improve the employment rate in young adults.

Tiara and Omia (2022) conducted the affiliation of emotional intelligence with performance of accounting lecturers. This study focuses on lecturers of the accounting study program of private universities in the province of Bali. This study aims to analyze the effect of emotional intelligence on the performance of lecturers in the accounting study program at private universities in Bali Province. The data collection method used is a questionnaire. The sample in this study amounted to 182 people. The analysis includes an instrument test, classical assumption test, normality test, linear regression, hypothesis testing, and coefficient of determination test using simple regression analysis with SPSS 14.0 for Windows program. The results show that emotional intelligence positively affects the performance of lecturers in the accounting study program. The study therefore, recommends that it is required to improve the emotional intelligence of the lecturers and the training of emotional intelligence involving a psychiatrist that supports improving lecturer performance is one of the tracks to develop us.

Nurul and Muafi (2023) conducted the influence of Islamic emotional intelligence and work-life balance on organizational commitment mediated by burnout. This study examines and analyses the effect of Islamic emotional intelligence, work-life balance, and burnout on organizational commitment. In addition, this study also examines and analyzes the role of burnout in mediating the effect of Islamic emotional intelligence and work-life balance on organizational commitment. Respondents in this study were female employees who worked at the Ministry of Religion in Pekanbaru, Riau, with a total of 73 respondents. The sampling technique was carried out by saturated sampling or census with SEM-PLS statistical analysis. The results showed that (i) Islamic emotional intelligence has an effect on organizational commitment, (ii) work-life balance has an effect on organizational commitment, (iii) burnout has an effect on organizational commitment, (iv) Islamic emotional intelligence has an effect on burnout, (v) work-life balance affects burnout, (vi) burnout can mediate the effect of Islamic emotional intelligence on organizational commitment, (vii) burnout can mediate the effect of work-life balance on organizational commitment. This research also has several recommendations that need to be considered by the organization as material for consideration in

improving development. Organizations need to hold personal approaches or discussions about personal problems face by face, because most female employees at the Ministry of Religion Pekanbaru Riau don't know what can trigger their emotions. Organizations should also do a term evaluation to monitor the results of the work, whether it is really good or just sober.

Elham, Mohammad, Hadi, Vahid and Mahdi (2023) examined the influence of emotional intelligence on academic stress. A Study with university of medical sciences students. The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of an intervention based on an emotional intelligence component on the coping skills of academic stress in medical students. This research has been done in two descriptive and quasi-experimental sections in the academic student. In order to determine the effect of emotional intelligence components on stress levels, this descriptive study was performed on 200 students. Then, a quasi-experimental study was then conducted to determine the effect of an emotional intelligence component-based educational intervention on academic stress coping skills. Data were collected through personal information questionnaire, Bradbury and Graves emotional intelligence questionnaire and Gadzella's academic stress questionnaire. Emotional intelligence components predicted 27.1% of the variance of academic stress among students. In parallel with the effect of education, the experimental group showed a statistically significant difference in the mean of each of the components of emotional intelligence and the overall score of academic stress ($p > 0.05$). The study concludes that Educational intervention based on emotional intelligence components can significantly help reduce students' academic stress. Therefore study recommends that appropriate training programs must be implemented in the universities.

Farah and Zulaikha (2022) examined the level of emotional intelligence in medical imaging students. This study is aimed to evaluate the average level of EI in medical imaging students whether it is significantly different from the EI value set at 2.5 (high level of emotional intelligence). This cross-sectional study used the adopted Emotional Intelligence Scale (EIS) questionnaire. Purposive sampling method was conducted on 89 medical imaging students. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 26. One sample T-test and Pearson correlation test were conducted with the significant p-values were set at <0.05 . The results showed that the medical imaging students' EI overall mean score was 3.84 (SD: 0.38) with p-value of <0.001 . There were also significant p-values of <0.001 for all 10 sub-dimensions of EIS. However, there is no significant correlation was found between level of emotional intelligence and year of study of the respondents 0.69 (R-value:-0.043). Significant high level of EI in medical imaging students could plausibly cause the students to have the ability to perceive themselves as efficient, enthusiastic, cheerful, satisfied, and always tend to stay optimistic in life, have greater self-control, able to endure pressure and manage tension, and are conscientious. The study concluded that high emotional intelligence students were predicted to be more poised for success in the future healthcare professions and industries. Therefore, the study recommended that it is important for them to become a person of emotionally intelligent. Particularly, in managing their emotional intelligence to improve and harmonize the relationship with the patient, colleagues, and public.

Andy and Azhar (2022) investigated Emotional Intelligence: Its importance to HE professional services team members during challenging times. In this context, leaders' abilities to manage emotions in the workplace appear to be at a premium. However emotionality remains under-explored both generally within HE and in non-academic contexts particularly. This article summarizes findings from research into the impact perceptions of managers' abilities to display Emotional Intelligence (EI) has on the wellbeing, attitudes and performance of staff within the context of a professional services team in one English university. It found perceptions of managers' EI could be a powerful influence on team members' mental health, including stress and anxiety. Furthermore, when managers were viewed as being Emotionally Intelligent, staff reported this significantly impacted their motivation and could lead to tangible improvements in core areas of job performance, including commitment, flexibility and discretionary effort. It recommends Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) consider placing greater emphasis on developing understanding of EI throughout their workforce while also building capacity in its practice amongst current and prospective managers.

Hu, X.; Li, Kumari, Ben, Khan, and Alkhuraydili, (2023) examined Relationship between Green Leaders' Emotional Intelligence and Employees' Green Behavior: A PLS-SEM Approach. In the present research, leaders' emotional intelligence (EI) is positioned as a mediating variable between GL and employees' green organizational citizenship behavior (GOCB). The data of this research comprised managerial and non-managerial staff from the manufacturing and service industries. A PLS-SEM was used to evaluate the relationship between the various factors among 422 employees. The empirical findings indicated that GL and GOCB had a favorable and robust relationship. The results of the study also suggested that a leader's EI mediates the influence of green leadership on their employees' green organizational citizenship behavior. The study concluded that Green leadership is essential in creating sustainable environmental behaviors among employees. It can strengthen leaders' EI, which successively helps them to garner positivity and foster an environment of mutual harmony and cooperation in the workplace to support pro-environmental policies.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

Descriptive research design was adopted in this study because it constitutes the blueprint for the measurement and analysis of data (Ernest, Matthew & Smauel, 2015). The purpose of descriptive survey design was to collect detailed and factual information that describes an existing phenomenon. This design deals with incidences of distribution and relationships among variables, it was deemed the best strategy to fulfill the objectives of this study.

3.2 Area of the Study

This study was undertaken within south-east of Nigeria. The South East (often written as South-East) is one of the six geopolitical zones of Nigeria representing both a geographic and political region of the country's inland southeast. It comprises five states – Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu, and Imo. The zone is bounded by the River Niger on the West, the riverine Niger Delta on the South, the flat North central to the North, and the Cross River on the East. It is divided between the Cross–Niger transition forests eco-regions in the south and the Guinean forest–savanna mosaic in the drier north. Culturally, the vast majority of the zone falls within Igbo land, the indigenous cultural homeland of the Igbo people, a group which makes up the largest ethnic percentage of the southeastern population. Although the South East is the smallest geopolitical zone, it contributes greatly to the Nigerian economy due to oil and natural gas reserves along with a growing industrialized economy.

3.3 Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised 13,163 academic staff of the five (5) federal universities in South-East, Nigeria (Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Michael Okpara University of Agricultural Umudike, University of Nigeria, Nsukka, Alex Ekwueme University, Ndufu-Alike, and Federal University of Technology, Owerri). See the breakdown of the population below:

Table 3.1: Population Distribution

S/N	Names of Federal Universities	Town	State	Number of Academic Staff
1	Nnamdi Azikiwe University	Awka	Anambra	2,702
2	Michael Okpara University of Agriculture	Umudike	Abia	2,421
3	University of Nigeria	Nsukka	Enugu	3,283
4	Alex Ekwueme University	Ndufu-Alike Ikwo	Ebonyi	2,234
5	Federal university of Technology	Owerri	Imo	2,523
	Total			13,163

Source: From Universities Personnel Departments 2023

3.4 Sample and Sampling Technique

Cooper and Schindler (2003) state that the size of a sample should be a function of the variation in the population parameter under study and the estimated precision by the researcher. Proportional sampling technique was employed in getting the sample based on the studied emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff. The sample size was determined using Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample formular. The sample formular was used because the population of study was so large, and rather difficult to manage without bias. The Krejcie and Morgan sample size statistical determination model is stated thus:

$$s = \frac{x^2 NP (1-P)}{d^2 (N-1) + x^2 P (1-P)}$$

Where:

S = Sample size

N = Population size (13,163)

p = Population proportion is taken as 0.5 since this would provide the maximum sample size

d = degree of accuracy expressed as a proportion

x^2 = Table value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at 5% confidence level (3.84)

$$s = \frac{3.84 \times 13,163 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}{0.05^2 (13,163 - 1) + 3.84 \times 0.5 (1-0.5)}$$

$$s = \frac{12636.48}{33.86}$$

$$= 373.19$$

$$s = 373$$

Thus, the sample size was 373 academic staff of the five Federal Universities in the South-east, Nigeria. Thereafter, the respondents were randomly selected from the academic staff of the five federal universities in south-east in order to give every member of the population equal chance of been selected for the study. This was done via balloting by writing “Yes” and “No” in paper and this was folded and every employee was asked to pick one. Those who picked “Yes” were selected for the study, while those who picked “No” were not included in the study. The targeted participants for the study are academic staff whose ranks range from

assistants lecturer up to the rank of professor. However, the proportion of the questionnaire administered to each of the five federal university was determined using Bowley's proportional allocation formula.

Thus:

$$nh = \frac{n \times Nh}{N}$$

Where:

nh = Number of copies of the questionnaire allocated to each university

n = Total sample size

Nh = Number of lecturers in each of the Federal Universities.

N = Population size

For Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka,

$$n = 373$$

$$Nh = 2,702$$

$$N = 13163$$

$$nh = \frac{373 \times 2702}{13163}$$

Thus, $nh = 76.57$

Approximately 77 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

For Michael Okpara University, Umudike

$$n = 373$$

$$Nh = 2,421$$

$$N = 13163$$

$$nh = \frac{373 \times 2421}{13163}$$

Thus, $nh = 68.6$

Approximately 69 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to Michael Okpara University, Umudike.

For University of Nigeria, Nsukka

$$n = 373$$

$$Nh = 3,283$$

$$N = 13163$$

$$nh = \frac{373 \times 3283}{13163}$$

Thus, $nh = 93.03$

Approximately 93 copies of questionnaire were distributed to University of Nigeria, Nsukka.

For Alex Ekwueme University, Ndufu-AlikeIkwo

$$n = 373$$

$$Nh = 2,234$$

$$N = 13163$$

$$nh = \frac{373 \times 2234}{13163}$$

Thus, $nh = 63.30$

Approximately 63 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to Alex Ekwueme University, Ndufu-Alike Ikwo.

For Federal University of Technology, Owerri

$n = 373$

$Nh = 2,523$

$N = 13163$

$$nh = \frac{373 \times 2523}{13163}$$

Thus, $nh = 71.49$

Approximately 72 copies of the questionnaire were distributed to Federal University of Technology, Owerri.

Table 2: Questionnaire Allocation to each of the Federal Universities

S/N	Federal Universities	Population	Questionnaire Allocated
1	Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka	2702	77
2	Michael Okpara University, Umudike	2421	69
3	University of Nigeria, Nsukka	3283	93
4	Alex Ekwueme University, Ndufu-AlikeIkwo	2234	63
5	Federal University of Technology, Owerri	2523	72
Total		13163	373

Source: Field Survey, 2023

3.5 Sources of Data

This study made use of primary and secondary data. The primary source of data were collected on a first-hand basis. This study made use of questionnaire to generate the primary data. Prior to the distribution of the questionnaire, secondary data were collected from relevant literature including journals, books, research papers, conference papers, government reports, and relevant electronic data, which informed the empirical study.

3.6 Instruments for Data Collection

The instrument that was employed for data collection is a questionnaire constructed by the researcher. The instrument consists of two parts. Part 1 captured the respondents' personal data. While the Part 2 of the instrument designed to elicit data on the effect of emotional intelligence on performance of academic staff. The response format is Likert 5-point scale. The response scoring is Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Undecided (UD), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

3.7 Validity of the Instrument

The study adopted face and content validity. The face and content validity were established by three lecturers in the Department of Business Administration who specialized in measurement and evaluation. The copies of the questionnaire together with the topic, objective of the study, research questions, and hypotheses were given to the three lecturers in measurement and evaluation, all from Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management Sciences, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University. Those lecturers were

required to scrutinize the items for clarity, appropriateness of language, relatedness to research questions and hypotheses. Their corrections and suggestions were incorporated into the final draft of the questionnaire.

3.8 Reliability of the Instrument

Test re-test method was carried out to achieve reliability of the instrument. This was done by administering 20 copies of the questionnaire to 20 Respondents. Thereafter, the responses were collated and recorded. After two weeks the researchers administered 20 copies of the questionnaire to the same 20 respondents and achieved the same result. It was observed that the degree of correlation and consistency was high. The Cronbach Alpha was used to determine the reliability of the instrument by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 23. The Cronbach Alpha value respectively for related emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff are in appendix II. According to the rule of thumb about Cronbach Alpha coefficient size, the higher the Cronbach Alpha, the higher the reliability coefficient. Based on the result, emotional intelligence: self-awareness (0.87), self-regulation (0.88), self-motivation (0.76), empathy (0.74), relationship management (0.90) and social skills (0.79) as independent variables while performance of academic staff: employee task performance (0.72), employee adaptive performance (0.70), employee contextual performance (0.82), employee counterproductive work behavior (0.88), employee proactive work behavior (0.92) and employee creativity (0.93) as dependent variables. It was concluded that all the six independent variables and the six dependent variables were reliable because they are under the Cronbachs Alpha acceptable threshold.

3.9 Method of Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using quantitative data analysis methods. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to present quantitative data in form of tables. Data from questionnaire was coded and entered into the computer using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Version 23) for analysis. The study employed simple percentage and linear regression analysis to determine the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. Emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff were regressed against the six independent variables and independent variable using the linear regression model. The study employed simple percentage analysis to answer research questions while Linear Regression Analysis (LRA) method was used in testing hypotheses in order to evaluate the effect of emotional intelligence on the performance of academic staff in federal universities in south east, Nigeria. The decision rule should be if the p-value is less than the 0.05 level of significance, we reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternative hypotheses.

3.10 Model Specification

This study adopted the following model; Daniel Goleman's model of *emotional intelligence* (1995) and model of *employee performance* by Koopmans, Berhnaards, Hildebrandt, vet, & Berk (2014) which state that

$$\text{Academic Performance} = Y (\text{TP, AP, CP, CWB, PWB, EC}) - \quad - \quad (1)$$

Y = Task Performance (TP)

Y = Adaptive Performance (AP)

Y = Contextual Performance (CP)

Y = Counterproductive Work Behavior (CWB)

Y = Proactive Work Behavior (PWB)

Y = Employee Creativity (EC)

Specifying equation (1) in an econometric form, we have:

$$EP = Y + X_1 TP + X_2 AP + X_3 CP + X_4 CWB + X_5 PWB + X_6 EC + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

Where:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \beta_5 X_5 + \beta_6 X_6 + \beta_n X_n + \epsilon$$

Where:

Y = dependent variable

α = Constant Term

β = Beta coefficients

X_1 to X_6 = Independent variables

ϵ = Error Term

X = Emotional Intelligence (EM)

X_1 = Self-Awareness (SA)

X_2 = Self-Regulation (SR)

X_3 = Self-Motivation (SM)

X_4 = Empathy (EM)

X_5 = Relationship Management (RM)

X_6 = Social Skills (SS).

4.1 Presentation of Data

Table 4.1: Presentation of Data Response Rate

This chapter deals with the presentation and analysis of the data obtained from the academic staff of some selected federal universities in South-eastern states of Nigeria. The study was conducted to examine the effect of emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff in federal universities in Southeast, Nigeria. A total of three hundred and seventy-three (373) copies of questionnaires were distributed, out of which, three hundred and forty-one (341) copies of questionnaires were fully completed and returned while thirty-two (32) 9% copies were not returned or not properly filled. This gives the response rate to be ninety-one percent (91%).

ITEMS DISTRIBUTED	NUMBER	PERCENTAGE
Copies of the questionnaire distributed	373	100
Copies of the questionnaire Returned	341	100
Copies of valid questionnaire	341	91%
Copies of the invalid questionnaire	32	9%
Total	341	100

Author's compilation 2023

4.1.1 Characteristics of the Respondents (Bio-data)

Table 4.1.1: Characteristics of the Respondents

S/N	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
1	Gender		
	Male	158	46.3
	Female	183	53.7
	Total 341	100	
2.	Age		
	Below 25years	53	15.5
	26-35 years	163	47.8
	36 years and above	125	36.7
	Total	341	100
3	Education Level		
	Postgraduate Degrees	341	100
	Total	341	341
4	How long have you worked in the organization?		
	0-5 yrs	64	18.8
	6-10 yrs	80	23.5
	11—15yrs	93	27.3
	16 yrs and above	104	30.1
	Total	341	100
5	University belonged.		
	UNIZIK, Awka	75	22.0
	MOUAAU, Abia	61	18.1
	UNN, Enugu	62	18.2
	AE-FUNAI Ebonyi	52	15.0
	FUTO, Owerri	91	27.0
	Total	341	100

Source: Computed from SPSS 26 Analysis

The results of table 4.1.1 shows that majority of the respondents are female (53.7%) and mostly are of the age bracket of 26-35years. From the data, it is clear that about 100% of the academic staff of the selected universities have their postgraduate degrees. The data also shows that 22% of the academic staff are from UNIZIK, Anambra State, 18.2% are from UNN, 27.0% are from FUTO, while 33.1% are drawn from MOUAAU, Abia and AE-FUNAI Ebonyi. However, the information gathered from the staff show that 18.8% of the staff have worked with the university in less than 5 years. 23.5% of them have worked with their respective universities between 6 years and 10 years, 27.3% of them have worked with the university for 11 – 15years, while the remaining 30.1% of the academic staff have worked with the university for over 16 years.

The presentation and interpretation indicate that majority of the academic staff are knowledgeable enough, with at least postgraduate degree. Some are male, while some are female. So, it is believed that they should be sensitive enough to know the effect of emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff in federal universities in South East, Nigeria.

4.2.1 Hypothesis One

Ho: Self-awareness has no significant positive effect on employee task performance in federal universities in south-east, Nigeria.

Ho₁: Self-awareness has significant positive effect on employee task performance in federal universities in south-east, Nigeria.

Table 4.2.1: Model Summary of linear regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.549 ^a	.322	.410	.891

a. Predictors: (Constant), self-awareness

As per Table 4.2.1, the regression model shows an R^2 of 0.322 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.41. This means that the model (self-awareness) predicts 41% of the variations of the academic staff self-awareness. This is significant at $p < 0.05$, which means a significant relationship exists between the independent variables of self-awareness of academic staff and the dependent variable, namely, employee task performance.

4.2.2 Hypothesis Two

Ho: Self-regulation has no significant positive effect on employee adaptive performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

Ho₁: Self-regulation has significant positive effect on employee adaptive performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria

Table 4.2.4: Model Summary of linear regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.601 ^a	.323	.561	.793

a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-regulation

Table 4.2.4 of the regression model depicts an R^2 of 0.323 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.561. This means that the model (self-regulation) predicts 56% of the variations of the academic staff self-regulation. This is significant at $p < 0.05$, which means a significant relationship exists between the independent variables of self-regulation of academic staff and the dependent variable, namely, employee adaptive performance.

4.2.3 Hypothesis Three

Ho: Self-motivation has no significant positive influence on employee contextual performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

Ho₁: Self-motivation has significant positive influence on employee contextual performance in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

Table 4.2.7: Model Summary of linear regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.471 ^a	.206	.341	.627

a. Predictors: (Constant), Self-motivation

Table 4.2.7 of the regression model shows that an R^2 of 0.206 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.341. This means that the model (self-motivation) predicts 34.1% of the variations of the academic staff self-motivation. This is significant at $p < 0.05$, which means a significant relationship

exists between the independent variables of self- motivation of academic staff and the dependent variable, namely, employee contextual performance.

4.2.4 Hypothesis Four

Ho: Empathy has no significant positive effect on employee counterproductive work behaviour in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

Ho₁: Empathy has no significant positive effect on employee counterproductive work behaviour in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

Table 4.2.10: Model Summary of linear regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.461 ^a	.213	.193	.658

a. Predictors: (Constant), Empathy

Table 4.2.10 of the regression model depicts an R^2 of 0.213 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.193. This means that the model (empathy) predicts 19.3% of the variations of the academic staff empathy. Therefore, the p-value which is greater ($p > 0.05$) than 0.05 indicate that there is no significant relationship existing between the independent variables of empathy of academic staff and the dependent variable (counterproductive work behaviour).

4.2.5 Hypothesis Five

Ho: Relationship management has no significant positive effect on employee proactive work behaviour in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

Ho₁: Relationship management has significant positive effect on employee proactive work behaviour in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

Table 4.2.13: Model Summary of linear regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.312 ^a	.291	.352	.510

a. Predictors: (Constant), Relationship management

As per Table 4.2.13 of the regression model depicts an R^2 of 0.291 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.352. This means that the model (relationship management) predicts 35.2% of the variations of the academic staff relationship management. This is significant at $p < 0.05$, which means a significant relationship exists between the independent variables of relationship management of academic staff and the dependent variable, namely, employee proactive work behaviour.

4.2.6 Hypothesis Six

Ho: Social skills have no significant positive effect on employee creativity in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

Ho₁: Social skills have significant positive effect on employee creativity in federal universities in south east, Nigeria.

Table 4.2.16: Model Summary of linear regression analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.310 ^a	.170	.482	.601

a. Predictors: (Constant), Social skills

Table 4.2.16 of the regression model depicts an R^2 of 0.170 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.482. This means that the model (social skill) predicts 48.2% of the variations of the academic staff

social skill. This is significant at $p < 0.05$, which means a significant relationship exists between the independent variables of social skill of academic staff and the dependent variable, namely, employee creativity.

5.2 Conclusion

This study used a quantitative methodology to examine the performance and emotional intelligence of academic staff in Federal Universities in South-East, Nigeria. There is a strong positive correlation between academic staff performance and emotional intelligence, as confirmed by the study's empirical results, which are endorsed by various emotional intelligence researchers. Examining academic staff members' emotional intelligence, the researcher found that emotional intelligence leadership is not applied well in the university and that academic staff members' emotional intelligence competencies are average, meaning they should work on improving them. Thus, the study concluded that understanding emotions and developing emotion regulation can help achieve educational goals and objectives and improve academic staff performance in Federal Universities in the South East, Nigeria'.

5.3 Recommendations

1. 'Nigerian university management should create more awareness about the importance of self-awareness among their staff through effective training of academic staff on self-awareness competencies. Additionally, academics should be trained on how to improve their self-confidence, which will enhance their confidence in their work, and consequently, improve their contributions to the university and the society'.
2. 'Federal universities in the South-East should prioritize management leadership training, with a focus on developing the adaptive behavior of employees. Training and learning enable academic staff to adopt self-regulation strategies, guiding students to effectively handle unpredictable environmental or work-related tasks and purposefully achieve improved employee adaptive performance'.
3. 'Federal universities in the South-East should organize training and activities to enhance self-leadership skills through continuous or routine self-leadership training, ensuring equal distribution across all university units, regardless of employee cadre.
4. 'Furthermore, federal university management should foster a harmonious atmosphere, encouraging mutual understanding, positive communication, and helping behaviors among workers. By cultivating a friendly culture and cooperative norms, employees can be shielded from excessive negative feelings'.
5. 'Academic staff at the universities should prioritize building strong relationships with their colleagues, students, and management, which will enhance their work strength and contribute to a friendly environment'.
6. 'Federal universities in the South-East should prioritize developing the social skills of academic staff to achieve emotional balance in their work attitude'.

5.4 Contributions to Knowledge

The major contribution of this study to knowledge is that emotional intelligence indicators have significant positive effect on academic staff performance indicators in Federal Universities in South-East, Nigeria.

This study is an addition to conceptual, theoretical, and empirical study on emotional intelligence and performance of academic staff in Federal Universities in South-East, Nigeria.

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